
High Middle Ages Aristocratic Networks through Alcuin's Letters and Digital Methods (c. 790-804)

Renato Da Silva*^{†1}

¹Universidade Federal Fluminense [Rio de Janeiro] – Brazil

Abstract

The writing of letters in the pre-modern world is a phenomenon that has been studied for decades. Epistolography, as it has been called, has mostly been studied through the analysis of the text that embody this form of communication. Lately, experts like Zweck (2018) and Richter (213) have pointed out that letters need to be understood within the larger context of what is called 'Epistolary Acts', which also encompass gift-giving, a specific medium, and the materiality of letters. Bovo has been keen on pointing out how epistolography can be a good starting point to build a form of Connected History of the Middle Ages (2021). Nelson has also highlighted how court culture (and specifically in the age of Charlemagne) was necessarily 'international' and how it was a crucible for innovations. Costrino (2020) has also pointed out that the trajectory of Alcuin's life has also pointed out how circulation and aristocratic connection could be an important part of intellectual, social, or even global History. Networks of people (or their 'biographies') of the Middle Ages have also been studied, focused on how both people and narratives (historiographical, hagiographical etc) can be explored through network theory (Gramsch et alii, 2017). Network analyses of narrative sources have also been used to explore the interpretation of measuring communication, its possibilities and limits in the Middle Ages (Fernández-Aceves, 2017). Nonetheless, historiography can be pushed forward by adding to those analyses topographical and geospatial data. In this sense, the current work focus on presenting the results of an ongoing research that analyses Alcuin's letters (790-804) in order to explore the levels and forms of aristocratic connectivity through Digital Methods. To achieve this objective, the work will produce graphs based on letters that contain gifts, attempting to understand how the phenomenon of gift giving is vital to produce aristocratic cohesion and consensus, and who received the gifts and how. The paper will also compare the results between gifts traded between women and men, considering how gendered these connections were. GIS will be used to map where the more connected people were, evaluating how the level of connectivity of the aristocrats might be related to the spatial transformations that were taking place in this context. The main hypothesis of the research is that through GIS and graph networks, Alcuin's letters can be a gateway to understand the sense of a Pan-European aristocratic cohesion that is built upon supralocal connections.

Keywords: Medieval History, Epistolography, Aristocratic Networks, Digital Methods

*Speaker

[†]Corresponding author: silva_renato@id.uff.br